

ANALYSIS OF STRAIN UNIFORMITIES IN ASYMMETRIC BI-STABLE COMPOSITE LAMINATES

Diankun Pan¹, Fuhong Dai¹

¹Center for Composite Materials and Structures, Harbin Institute of Technology
Building A, Yikuang Street 2, Nangang District, Harbin, China
Email: daifh@hit.edu.cn, web page: <http://www.hit.edu.cn/>

Keywords: Strain distributions, Asymmetric laminates, Bi-stable, Cured shape

ABSTRACT

Asymmetric composite laminates can have a bi-stable response, due to during the elevated temperature of manufacturing process, and residual thermal stresses lead to a curved shape at room temperature. These laminates can have two stable configurations at room temperature: cylindrical configuration I with a major curvature in x axis and cylindrical configuration II with an opposite curvature in orthogonal y axis. The large deflections that can be achieved by snap-through from one configuration to another, along with a need for small and removable energy input, make them of interest for a wide range of engineering application, notably morphing application in the aerospace industry. After 30 years of research efforts the shapes and response of asymmetric laminates of general layup have been well characterized. In this work, the Extended Classical Lamination Theory is considered as a basic approach to analysis the strains distribution of the bi-stable laminates. The paper begins by outlining the existing modeling formulation for arbitrary layup laminates and deriving an analytical formulation to an orthogonal laminate geometry. It is found that the distributions of strains are uniform, and the magnitudes of strains are closely related to the configurations. The strain of x direction is much more than y direction in configuration A with a major curvature in x axis. The similar situation also exists in configuration B. The changes of strains during snap-through are discussed, and compared with the Finite Element Models and experiments. The strain gauge test is carried out in experiments. The results show that the distributions of Models and experiments. The strain gauge test is carried out in experiments. The results show that the distributions of strain changes are also even.

1 INTRODUCTION

Asymmetric composite laminates have been considered for adaptive structures due to the relatively low power requirement to achieve large structural deformations [1, 2]. Due to the unbalanced stacking sequence, asymmetric laminates have an anisotropic response to the elevated temperatures experienced during manufacture. This leads to residual thermal stresses resulting in a curved deformation. Under certain geometric conditions, the thermal distortion can lead to two stable configurations with approximately cylindrical curvatures. Figure 1 shows a square [02/902]_T laminate with two stable shapes of equal curvature in opposite directions. By applying relatively small and removable energy input, the change from one stable state to another is achievable, resulting in a large deformation that are of interest for many engineering application [3].

Early work in this field focused primarily on modeling of the shapes of laminates with ply orientations of 0 and 90 deg, commonly referred to as cross-ply stacking sequences. The modeling was on a Rayleigh-Ritz approach minimizing the total strain energy of the laminate. The original model of Hyer [4] was based on the Rayleigh-Ritz method which consists in searching approximate displacement solutions, satisfying kinematic boundary conditions. This procedure involved the employment of moderate order polynomial functions for the description of the displacement. The predictions of the Hyer's original model are shown in agreement with experiments on [0/90]_T square plates and Finite Element Models (FEM). Other contribution based on displacement assumptions came from Jun and Hong [5, 6]. The displacement functions were used to obtain the strains needed to compute the laminate strain energy. Dano and Hyer [7] used directly for the first time approximation

for the laminate mid-plane strains. Initially they used a set of complete polynomials with 28 unknown coefficients, but then they realized that use of 14 coefficients was enough. This approach is named Extended Classical Lamination Theory (ECLT). Based on the ECLT, bi-stable laminate design for a reversible snap-through in adaptive structures has recently been studied reducing the number of unknown coefficients base on ply design, and an analytical approach has been presented. In this work the ECLT is considered as a basic approach.

Figure 1: Two stable shapes of a square $[0_2/90_2]_T$ laminate.

2 ANALYTICAL MODEL

The analytical model used to calculate the strains of asymmetric laminates of arbitrary layup was introduced by Dano and Hyer [7], and is a nonlinear extension to classical laminated plate theory. This model has previously been validated by both experimental [8-10] and finite element modeling studies [11, 12]. The coordinate system used is that defined in Figure 1, where the geometric center of the laminate sits at the origin and ply orientations are measured from the x-axis. The out-of-plane displacement in the z direction, w is assumed to be of the form:

$$w(x, y) = \frac{1}{2}(ax^2 + by^2 + cxy) \quad (1)$$

The mid-plane strains, including geometrical nonlinearity according to the von Kaman hypothesis, are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_x^0 &= \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 &= \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)^2 \\ \varepsilon_{xy}^0 &= \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Where u^0 and v^0 are the in-plane displacements in the x and y directions, respectively. The mid-plane strains are approximated by third-order polynomials. Dano and Hyer [7] considered the complete third-order polynomials and found that terms with powers of x and y that sum to an odd number are always zero. This relationship is confirmed analytically for all laminates considered in this paper. Therefore, the form of the mid-plane strains can be reduced to the polynomials of Eq. (3):

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_x^0 &= d_1 + d_2x^2 + d_3xy + d_4y^2 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 &= d_5 + d_6x^2 + d_7xy + d_8y^2 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Using Eqs.(1-3) and introducing the additional shape coefficients $d_{9,11}$ resulting from integration of the mid-plane strains, expressions for the in-plane displacement u^0 and v^0 can be determined:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u^0(x, y) &= d_1x + d_9y + \frac{1}{2}\left(d_3 - \frac{1}{2}ac\right)x^2y + \left(d_4 - \frac{c^2}{8}\right)xy^2 + \frac{1}{3}\left(d_2 - \frac{1}{2}a^2\right)x^3 + \frac{1}{3}d_{11}y^3 \\
 v^0(x, y) &= d_9x + d_5y + \frac{1}{2}\left(d_7 - \frac{1}{2}bc\right)xy^2 + \left(d_6 - \frac{c^2}{8}\right)x^2y + \frac{1}{3}\left(d_8 - \frac{1}{2}b^2\right)y^3 + \frac{1}{3}d_{10}x^3 \quad (4)
 \end{aligned}$$

From Eq.(2) shear strain is:

$$\varepsilon_{xy}^0 = \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} = 2d_9 + \left(4d_4 + ac - \frac{c^2}{2}\right)xy + \left(d_{10} + \frac{d_3}{2} + \frac{ac}{4}\right)x^2 + \left(d_{11} + \frac{d_7}{2} + \frac{ac}{4}\right) \quad (5)$$

The total strain energy of the laminate W can then be expressed as the integral of strain-energy density over the volume of the laminate:

$$W = \int_{-L_x/2}^{L_x/2} \int_{-L_y/2}^{L_y/2} \int_{-H/2}^{H/2} \frac{1}{2} c_{ijkl} \varepsilon_{ij} \varepsilon_{kl} - \alpha_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij} \Delta T dx dy dz \quad (6)$$

Where the subscripts ij and kl refer to all combinations of x , y , and xy directions, c_{ijkl} 's are elastic constants, α_{ij} 's are constants relating to the thermal expansion coefficients, L_x and L_y are the platform side lengths of the laminate, H is the total laminate thickness, ΔT is the temperature change from cure, and ε_{ij} 's and ε_{kl} 's are the total strains defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \varepsilon_x &= \varepsilon_x^0 - za \\
 \varepsilon_y &= \varepsilon_y^0 - zb \\
 \varepsilon_{xy} &= \varepsilon_{xy}^0 - zc
 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Where z is the distance from the laminate mid-plane and a , b , and c are out-of-plane shape coefficients defined by Eq.(1). Expansion of Eq.(5) results in an expression for the total energy, which is a function of the material and geometric properties, the temperature change from cure, and the set of shape coefficients a , b , c , d_1, \dots, d_{11} .

Replacing Eqs.(3) and (5) in total strains of Eqs. (7), the strain field of the basic approach is given by:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \varepsilon_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} d_1 + d_2x^2 + d_3xy + d_4y^2 \\ d_5 + d_6x^2 + d_7xy + d_8y^2 \\ 2d_9 + \left(4d_4 + ac - \frac{c^2}{2}\right)xy + \left(d_{10} + \frac{d_3}{2} + \frac{ac}{4}\right)x^2 + \left(d_{11} + \frac{d_7}{2} + \frac{ac}{4}\right) \end{Bmatrix} - z \begin{Bmatrix} a \\ b \\ c \end{Bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

For equilibrium, the minimum energy states require:

$$f_i = \frac{\partial W}{\partial e_i} = 0, \quad i=1 \dots 14 \quad (9)$$

Where e_i 's are coefficients a , b , c , d_1, \dots, d_{11} . The results in 14 nonlinear equations to be solved are substituted into Eqs.(8) to find the strains of stable shapes.

3 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Finite element analysis (FEA) is also conducted in this study. The commercial code, ABAQUS, is used in the analysis. The laminate is modeled with shell element S4R, which is one doubly curved thin/thick element with reduced integration and hour glass control. FEA requires there is no rigid body motion so enough boundary conditions need to be applied to the laminates. The center of the laminate was clamped, which means all the six degrees of freedom were constrained to be 0. A imperfection is imposed to find all the stable solutions. The imperfection is realized by applying one slight force in favor of one stable solution and then eliminating this force after the stable solution is reached. Large

deformation effects are considered, and a temperature field reflecting the curing process is applied to the FEA model. Finally, the two stable configurations predicted by FEA are shown in the Figure 2.

Figure 2: FEA predicted two stable configurations.

4 EXPERIMENT

The laminate used for the experimental study was carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) $[0_2/90_2]$ laminate consisting of four plies, each of 0.125mm thickness. A square laminate of size 300mm was manufactured using standard layup procedure using an intermediate carbon fibre-thermoset prepreg sheet. The material properties are showed in Table 1. The manufacturing process involved an autoclave cure cycle with a maximum temperature of 150°C and a pressure of 0.3MPa. The laminate was placed in a flat mould and covered by a vacuum bag during the cure cycle. The two stable configurations of experimental sample are shown in Figure 2.

Properties		Prepreg
E_1	[GPa]	162
E_2	[GPa]	9.6
ν_{12}	–	0.32
G_{12}	[GPa]	4.5
α_1	$[10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}]$	-0.1
α_2	$[10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}]$	2.7

Table 1: Mechanical properties of material.

Figure 3: Stable configurations of experimental sample.

To confirm the strain distribution of asymmetric composite laminates, the strain was measured by strain gauges. Nine points were selected to bond strain gauges. The positions of strain gauges are illustrated in Figure 3(a). The NO.5 is placed in the center of the laminate, and the others are located on the edges of square which is concentric with the profile of the laminate and scaled down. The strain

gauges were bonded on the curved surface of laminate. Thus, the initial state of strain gauges is zero at one configuration, and the strain gauges can obtain the variation when the bi-stable laminate snap through from one configuration to the other one. There are two strain gauges in the same measured point with two directions (x -direction and y -direction) to confirm the response of strain in the snap through process. Additionally, the two process (configuration I to II and configuration II to I) were measured respectively. Undergone repeated measurements for every process, the average strain values were obtain.

Figure 4: (a) The positions of strain gauges; (b) The two configurations of experimental sample with strain gauges.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

5.1 Strain distribution of configurations

The Extended Classical Lamination Theory (ECLT) is employed as the analytical model to illustrate the strain distribution of bi-stable asymmetric composite laminates. The geometry of laminate in the z -direction is shown in the Figure 5. The strains (ϵ_x and ϵ_y) of top-plane (orange color) and bottom-plane (pink color) in the two direction (x -direction and y -direction) are computed respectively at the two stable configurations which are shown in Figure 1. The results of strains distribution at two stable configurations are shown in Figure 6 and 7. The strain distribution is uniformity, despite the results in Figure 6 and 7 are in an extravagant way. The max value of strain is on the axis of symmetry (max value of ϵ_x is on the x -axis and max value of ϵ_y is on the y -axis), the min value is on the edge (min value of ϵ_x is on the x -edges and min value of ϵ_y is on the y -edges). However, the gap is just $15\mu\epsilon$ between the minimum and maximum.

In the assumption of ECLT, the stable configurations of square asymmetric bistable laminate is supposed to be cylindrical shape. Thus, the curvature at one configuration is constant, and the deformation is uniform in the cooling process. The strain of stable configuration obtained from the cooling process are similar due to the even deformation.

Figure 5: Four-ply laminate geometry.

For the configuration A, the ε_x is negative on the top-plane, and positive on the bottom-plane. It means that the compressive strain in x -direction exists on the bottom-plane and tensile strain exists on the top-plane. Furthermore, the absolute value ε_x of bottom-plane is larger than top-plane. Nevertheless, the strain in the y -direction on the two planes are negative and close to each other. In contrast to the configuration B, the ε_y perform tensile on the top-plane and compressive on the bottom-plane. The value ε_y of top-plane is similar with ε_x on the bottom-plane of configuration A, and the value ε_y of bottom-plane is same with ε_x on the top-plane of configuration A. The similar phenomenon exists between ε_x of configuration B and ε_y of configuration A.

Another notable point is that the largest strain reflects the feature of stable configuration. For configuration A, the principal curvature is in the x -direction when the largest strain is ε_x . The largest strain is ε_y when the principal curvature is in the y -direction for configuration B. Therefore, the magnitudes of strains are closely related to the configurations.

Figure 6: Strain distribution of configuration A.

Figure 7: Strain distribution of configuration B.

5.2 Strain variation distribution in snap-through process

The strain gauges were bonded on the bottom-plane of the bistable laminate. Thus, the strain gauges are in the compressive state when the initial state is configuration A, and the strain gauges

change to tensile state when the laminate snap from configuration A to B. Hence, the strain measured by strain gauges are positive in the snap-through process of configuration A to B. On the contrary, the strain are negative in the snap-through process of configuration B to A. The experimental results of measured points are shown in the Figure 8. At nine measured points, the strain variation in the snap-through process are basically similar. This illustrates the strain variation distribution in the snap-through process are uniform. It truly reflects that the strain distribution of square asymmetric bistable laminate are even.

It is found that the $\delta\varepsilon_y$ is much more than $\delta\varepsilon_x$ in the two snap processes. This is due to the plane on which strain gauges bonded is the bottom-plane. The experimental results matches to the theoretical results of the strain variation very well. The $\delta\varepsilon_x$ is much more than $\delta\varepsilon_y$ on the top-plane. This is explained that the deformation in the y -direction are much more than x -direction on the bottom-plane, no matter what the snap-process.

Figure 8: Experimental strain variation of measured points

The points along the path which is shown in the Figure 4(a) are selected to be the analysis object. The theoretical results, FEA results and experimental results of the selected path are compared in the Figure 9. The theoretical results are well agreement with the FEA results. The $\delta\varepsilon_y$ of experiment agree with the FEA and theory well. However, there are differences in $\delta\varepsilon_x$ between experiment and theory due to experimental error. The theoretical results are shown as straight lines, while the FEA results exist some fluctuations. It is mainly because that the influence of boundary conditions is considered in FEA. However, the significant consequence that the strain variation distribution is even in this bistable laminate is confirmed.

Figure 9: Strain variation distribution of configuration A-B

6 CONCLUSIONS

The Extended Classed Lamination Theory which is used to predict the configurations of asymmetric composite laminates, is considered as a basic approach to analysis the strains distribution of the bi-stable laminates. It is found that the distributions of strains are uniform, and the magnitudes of strains are closely related to the configurations. The strain of x direction is much more than y direction in configuration A with a principal curvature in x axis. The variation of strains during snap-through process are discussed. The strain gauge test is carried out in experiments to confirm the strains variation distribution. The experimental results agree with the theoretical results and FEA. The results show that the distributions of strain variation are also even.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant No.10502016 and 10872058).

REFERENCES

- [1] Diaconu, C. G., Weaver, P. M., and Mattioni, F. "Concepts for morphing airfoil sections using bi-stable laminated composite structures," *Thin-Walled Structures* Vol. 46, No. 6, 2008, pp. 689-701.
- [2] Mattioni, F., Weaver, P., Friswell, M., and Potter, K. Modelling and applications of thermally induced multistable composites with piecewise variation of lay-up in the planform, *Collection of Technical Papers-AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference, American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics Inc., Reston, VA.* 2007, pp. 20191-4344.
- [3] Mattioni, F., Weaver, P. M., Potter, K. D., and Friswell, M. I. The application of thermally induced multistable composites to morphing aircraft structures, *The 15th International Symposium on: Smart Structures and Materials & Nondestructive Evaluation and Health Monitoring.* International Society for Optics and Photonics, 2008, pp. 693012-693012-11.
- [4] Hyer, M. W. "The room-temperature shapes of four-layer unsymmetric cross-ply laminates," *Journal of Composite Materials* Vol. 16, No. 4, 1982, pp. 318-340.
- [5] Jun, W., and Hong, C. "Effect of residual shear strain on the cured shape of unsymmetric cross-ply thin laminates," *Composites science and technology* Vol. 38, No. 1, 1990, pp. 55-67.
- [6] Jun, W., and Hong, C. "Cured shape of unsymmetric laminates with arbitrary lay-up angles," *Journal of reinforced plastics and composites* Vol. 11, No. 12, 1992, pp. 1352-1366.
- [7] Dano, M.-L., and Hyer, M. W. "Thermally-induced deformation behavior of unsymmetric laminates," *International Journal of Solids and Structures* Vol. 35, No. 17, 1998, pp. 2101-2120.
- [8] Betts, D. N., Kim, H. A., and Bowen, C. R. "Modeling and optimization of bistable composite laminates for piezoelectric actuation," *Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures* Vol. 22, No. 18, 2011, pp. 2181-2191.
- [9] Betts, D. N., Kim, H. A., Bowen, C. R., and Inman, D. J. Optimization of piezoelectric bistable composite plates for broadband vibrational energy harvesting, *SPIE Smart Structures and Materials+ Nondestructive Evaluation and Health Monitoring.* International Society for Optics and Photonics, 2012, pp. 83412Q-83412Q-9.
- [10] Betts, D. N., Salo, A. I., Bowen, C. R., and Kim, H. A. "Characterisation and modelling of the cured shapes of arbitrary layup bistable composite laminates," *Composite Structures* Vol. 92, No. 7, 2010, pp. 1694-1700.
- [11] Bowen, C. R., Betts, D. N., Giddings, P. F., Salo, A., and Kim, H. A. "A Study of Bistable Laminates of Generic Lay - Up for Adaptive Structures," *Strain* Vol. 48, No. 3, 2012, pp. 235-240.
- [12] Ren, L. "A theoretical study on shape control of arbitrary lay-up laminates using piezoelectric actuators," *Composite Structures* Vol. 83, No. 1, 2008, pp. 110-118.